

High Performance Cuk Converter Controller

(Rekabentuk Sistem Kawalan Penukar Cuk Berprestasi Tinggi)

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ABSTRACT

In today's energy systems, many equipment operates with Direct Current (DC) voltage. However, normal power supply may not always be able to provide the voltage level required for the operation of these devices. As a result, DC-DC converters are utilised to achieve the desired voltage values for equipment that operates at various DC voltage levels. The Cuk converter, which has a low output ripple voltage and can work in both Buck and Boost modes, is the most popular. A continuous current at both the converter's input and output is a significant advantage of the Cuk converter. The Cuk converter has a lot of reactive components and puts a lot of current stress on the switch. The Cuk converter uses an additional inductor and capacitor to store energy. Because the feedback loop must maintain regulation, some form of compensation is unavoidable in order to maintain loop stability. Controlling the load voltage based on changeable supply voltage, reference voltage, frequency and load power is the scope of the control methods. The PI controller is the most extensively utilised controller in industrial settings where system speed is not a concern. OCC method is nonlinear method that uses the concept of control of average value of switching variable at every cycle. FLC is the simplest controller because it does not involve metamathematical module and famous in the industry where speed is the most important. The performances of PI, OCC and FLC controllers were compared with respect to performance parameters such as steady state error, voltage overshoot, ripple percentage, settling time and rise time. When the results obtained were evaluated as a whole, it was observed that FLC achieved the desired reference with less rise and settling time. In PI output voltage, it has less steady state error compare others. In OCC, the output voltage has less ripple percentage compare others. In this study, modeling and controller applications of Cuk converter are realized by using MATLAB / SIMULINK program.

Keywords: Converter, Cuk, System, Controller, PI, OCC, FLC

ABSTRAK

Marcapada ini terdapat banyak peralatan menggunakan voltan arus terus-ke-arus terus (AT-AT). Sehubungan itu pelbagai aras arus terus ke arus terus (AT-AT) diperlukan di dalam sesebuah mesin kerana terdapat pelbagai jenis litar. Oleh itu, agak mustahil untuk mendapatkan voltan keluaran yang diperlukan sekiranya hanya satu aras tenaga yang dibekalkan tanpa penukar arus terus-ke-arus terus (AT-AT) yang membekalkan pelbagai nilai voltan keluaran mengikut keperluan. Penukar arus terus-ke-arus terus (AT-AT) yang akan dibincangkan adalah penukar Cuk yang menyediakan voltan keluaran lebih tinggi ataupun voltan keluaran yang rendah berbanding voltan masukan. Kelebihan penukar Cuk ialah arus berterusan di tempat masuk dan keluar penukar. Kelemahan penukar Cuk adalah mempunyai komponen reaktif yang banyak dan tinggi tekanan arus pada di suis. Penukar Cuk menggunakan dua pendaras dan dua pemuat untuk menyimpan tenaga. Penukar Cuk memerlukan sebuah pengawal untuk menyuap balik dan memampas ralat pada voltan keluaran kepada litar semula untuk proses litar yang lengkap. Beberapa jenis pemampas diperlukan dan tidak dapat dielakkan untuk mencapai kestabilan pada voltan keluaran. Oleh itu, fokus akan diberikan kepada kawalan pada voltan di beban mengikut pemboleh ubah voltan masukan, voltan rujukan, frekuensi dan nilai beban. Setelah dikaji kawalan PI, adalah kawalan yang paling popular digunakan dalam industri di mana kelajuan tidak menjadi isu utama. OCC pula kawalan cara tidak kelulurusan yang menggunakan purata konsep jumlah purata pada pemboleh ubah pada suis pada setiap pusingan. Kawalan FLC pula sebuah kawalan mudah tanpa menggunakan model matematik dan popular dalam industri di mana kelajuan menjadi aspek keutamaan. Prestasi semua kawalan akan dibandingkan dan dianalisis berdasarkan beberapa aspek seperti masa naik, masa penetapan, voltan terlajak, ralat keadaan mantap dan peratus riak. Apabila keputusan dianalisis secara holistik, pengawal FLC mencapai voltan rujukan dengan masa naik dan masa penetapan yang pendek berbanding pengawal-pengawal yang lain. Pengawal PI pula mempunyai ralat keadaan mantap yang paling rendah antara pengawal-pengawal yang lain. Kelebihan OCC pula

mempunyai peratus riak yang paling rendah. Dalam kajian ini reka bentuk kawalan penukar Cuk gelung terbuka dan gelung tertutup disimulasikan menggunakan program MATLAB/SIMULINK .

Kata Kunci: Penukar Cuk; FLC; OCC; PI; Pengawal

INTRODUCTION

Switching circuits can convert a certain dc voltage to another precise level are known as dc to dc converters. Buck, Boost, Buck–Boost, Cuk, Zeta, and Sepic are the most common dc/dc converters. The dc to dc converters are widely applied in distributed generation resource, power factor correction ,air-space industry ,cranes ,vehicles ,electrical motors and renewable energy resources such as fuel cells and photovoltaic.(Babaei & Seyed Mahmoodieh 2014) Cuk converter has many active components and has higher switching stress to the switch. Cuk converter use additional capacitor and inductor for saving energy. Due to the feedback loop is required to keep on regulation, some type of compensation is inevitable to satisfy the loop stability. Next, simulation output voltage is slightly difference to calculated output voltage for open loop due to internal resistance. Without a controller in open loop the output voltage has a higher ripple percentage and not robust.(Kannan et al. 2017)

Effect of controller will be analyzed based on changing variable that is input voltage, reference voltage and load value.(Marimuthu & Umamaheswari 2019) The main concern is to identify which controller is the best that give output voltage has less settling time, rise time, ripple percentage, steady state error and made Cuk converter operating in high performance. Specifications of DC-DC converters include precise acceleration control, excellent efficiency, quick dynamic response, and the use of fewer power switches. High performance means that when changing the input voltage, reference voltage and load value the output voltage still follow the time and reference voltage. Hence Cuk converter can be chosen as the higher order converter for the implementation of the inverter.

The main difference between DC-DC converters is that they use different topologies. In this study, we used a Cuk converter which is a type of Cuk switch. Its main advantage is that it has continuous input and output currents.(Arun Srinivas et al. 2020)

The control strategy of a converter can be achieved by controlling the S switch's off state or on state. The multiply operating modes of the converter are shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: Circuits of the converter for on/off states of the switches during;(a)On state,(b)Off state

The two parts of the converter circuit are divided into two components, which are described in Figure 1. When the transistor switch is turned on, current through inductor L1, rises. At the same time, the voltage of capacitor C1 is lowered to prevent the diode D1 from acting as a reverse bias. When the input voltage is switched on, the forward biased D1 of diode is used to charge the capacitor C1 and the energy is transferred to the load through L2.(Pratiwi et al. 2020)

The Cuk converter can vary the voltage depending on the duty cycle. It can also step the voltage up or down. The Cuk converter contains the series inductors at both input and output, so it has much lower current ripple in both circuits.(Soedibyo et al. 2016). The quality of the output voltage is an important parameter, and it should have the least amount of ripple as possible. Furthermore, the switching current stress in these converters should be kept to a minimum. In this study, three controller has been chosen for Cuk controller which are OCC, PI and FLC.

The one-cycle control (OCC) methodology is a nonlinear control method has advantage of the switching converters pulsed and nonlinear nature to accomplish quick dynamic control of the switched variable's average value.(Ćuk 1995) After a transient, the average value of the switched variable only requires one switching cycle to achieve a new steady-state.

Between the reference signal and the average value of the switched variable, there is no steady-state or dynamic error.(Kasthala 2017) Fast dynamic responsiveness, great power source perturbation, robust performance, and automatic switching error correction are all features of this approach. It has been widely used in dc-dc conversion, particularly in buck converters , power amplifiers as control methods ,power factor correction ,active shunt power filters , multi-input

DC-DC converters.(Kannan et al. 2017)On the other hand, OCC has a faster transient reaction, a shorter settling time, and a lower maximum deviation from steady state than PI control. The steady state error of PI control is quite small. When the load is modified when OCC is implemented, some spikes may occur. The Cuk converter with PI control, does not have these spikes.(Bildirici & Karaarslan 2017).

The second controller in this study are Fuzzy Logic controller (FLC). The most notable aspect of fuzzy control, which has recently emerged as a key competitor to classical controllers in the field of control, is that it relieves the designer of mathematical procedures. Fuzzy logic-based controllers are currently used in practically every industry, from vehicle brake systems to washing machines and freezers to factory product quality control systems (Priyadarshi et al. 2019).

To construct the controller in the classic types of controls (P, PI, and PID), a number of mathematical expressions must be examined. Although this procedure is straightforward for linear systems, it necessitates the completion of complicated mathematical operations in the case of nonlinear systems. It is not necessary to analyse the mathematical expressions when developing an FLC for any linear or non-linear system.

Fuzzification, rule base, and defuzzification are the three main components of the fuzzy logic controller (YILMAZ et al. 2020), which was first employed by Mamdani in 1974. Figure 2 illustrates the FLC basic block diagram.

FIGURE 2. Basic block of FLC controller

According to Fig. 2, the error (e) and change of error (de) refers to inputs of the system and, the control signal (u) refers to the output system.

Because of its simple form and implementation, the Proportional-Integral PI Controller is the last controller in this study that is most used to control the DC-DC converter output voltage. A PI controller uses the error signal as the control loop's feedback(Devi & Srivani 2016).A proportional control system and an integrated control system are coupled to control a plant in a PI control system. The ability of a PI control system to modify the plant according to the set-point value while maintaining the plant position steady at a preset set-point value and having a faster response time are examples of strong performance. The exact constants needed in each of these control systems are proportional (K_p) and integral (I) to get the best

results on the performance of PI controllers .This constant value must be established in order to achieve good control results, including faster response times, more steady output, and low overshoot error values. (Karaarslan 2018) The diagram of the PI controller block used for the proposed system is represented in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3. Block Diagram PI controller

Figure 3 is a schematic of a PI controller. Minimizing the error signal is one of the control functions. The error signal is the difference between the desired and actual magnitude. The controller will be predisposed to speed up or slow down the achievement of the target settings as a result of this difference.(Shoumi et al. 2020)

METHODOLOGY

Open loop Cuk Converter

In open loop, Cuk converter can increase and reduce the output voltage based on the duty cycle. The series inductors are present at both the input and output of the Cuk converter, resulting in substantially lower current ripple in both circuits. The switch duty cycle can be used to calculate the average output voltage.(Asadi et al. 2017) Duty cycle,

$$D = \frac{-V_o}{V_s - V_o} \quad (1)$$

where, D is on time duration of switch/ total switching time period.

$$\text{Output voltage, } V_o = \frac{-DV_s}{1-D}$$

For open loop, two simulation were done to study the effect of duty cycle in output voltage, the first simulation the duty ratio was 0.4 and the parameter were calculated in this equation:

Duty cycle

$$D = \frac{-V_o}{V_s - V_o} = \frac{12}{18 - (-12)} = 0.4 \quad (1)$$

Inductor current of inductance I_{L1}

$$I_{L1} = \frac{P_s}{V_s} = \frac{40}{18} = 2.222 \text{ V} \quad (1)$$

Inductor current of inductance I_{L2}

$$I_{L2} = \frac{P_s}{-V_o} = \frac{40}{-12} = 3.333 \text{ A} \quad (2)$$

Rate of change inductor ΔI_{L1}

$$\Delta I_{L1} = I_{L1} \times 10\% = 2.222 \times 10\% = 0.222 \text{ A} \quad (3)$$

Rate of change inductor ΔI_{L2}

$$\Delta I_{L2} = I_{L2} \times 10\% = 3.333 \times 10\% = 0.333 \text{ A} \quad (5)$$

Inductor value, L_1

$$L_1 = \frac{V_S D}{\Delta I_{L1} f_s} = \frac{(18)(0.4)}{(0.222)(50000)} = 649 \mu\text{H} \quad (4)$$

Inductor value, L_2

$$L_2 = \frac{V_S D}{\Delta I_{L2} f_s} = \frac{(18)(0.4)}{(0.333)(50000)} = 432 \mu\text{H} \quad (5)$$

Capacitor value, C_2

$$C_2 = \frac{1 - D}{r_8 L_2 f^2} = \frac{1 - 0.4}{(0.01)(8)(432 \mu\text{H})(50000)^2} = 6.94 \mu\text{H} \quad (6)$$

Rate of change capacitor, ΔV_{C1}

$$\Delta V_{C1} = (V_S - V_O) r_{C1} = (18 - (-12))(0.01) = 0.3 \text{ A} \quad (7)$$

Load resistance, R

$$R = \frac{(V_o)(V_o)}{P} = \frac{(12)(12)}{40} = 3.6 \Omega \quad (8)$$

Capacitor value, C_1

$$C_1 = \frac{V_o D}{R f \Delta V_{C1}} = \frac{(12)(0.4)}{(5)(0.3)(50000)} = 64 \mu\text{H} \quad (9)$$

For second simulation the duty ratio that has been chosen is 0.6 to make sure the Cuk converter working in Boost mode to increase the input voltage, the calculation for parameter:

Duty cycle, D

$$D = \frac{-V_o}{V_S - V_O} = \frac{18}{12 - (-18)} = 0.6 \quad (10)$$

Inductor current of inductance, I_{L1}

$$I_{L1} = \frac{P_s}{V_s} = \frac{40}{12} = 3.33 \text{ A} \quad (11)$$

Inductor current of inductance, I_{L2}

$$I_{L2} = \frac{P_s}{-V_o} = \frac{40}{18} = 2.22 \text{ A} \quad (12)$$

Rate of change inductor, ΔI_{L1}

$$\Delta I_{L1} = I_{L1} \times 10\% = 3.333 \times 10\% = 0.333 \text{ A} \quad (13)$$

Rate of change inductor ΔI_{L2}

$$\Delta I_{L2} = I_{L2} \times 10\% = 2.222 \times 10\% = 0.222 \text{ A} \quad (14)$$

Inductor value, L_1

$$L_1 = \frac{V_S D}{\Delta I_{L1} f_s} = \frac{(12)(0.6)}{(0.333)(50000)} = 432 \mu\text{H} \quad (15)$$

Inductor value, L_2

$$L_2 = \frac{V_S D}{\Delta I_{L2} f_s} = \frac{(12)(0.6)}{(0.222)(50000)} = 649 \mu\text{H} \quad (16)$$

Capacitor value, C_2

$$C_2 = \frac{1 - D}{r_8 L_2 f^2} = \frac{1 - 0.6}{(0.01)(8)(432 \mu\text{H})(50000)^2} = 4.29 \mu\text{H} \quad (17)$$

Rate of change capacitor, ΔV_{C1}

$$\Delta V_{C1} = (V_S - V_O) r_{C1} = (12 - (-18))(0.01) = 0.3 \text{ A} \quad (18)$$

Load value, R

$$R = \frac{(V_o)(V_o)}{P} = \frac{(18)(18)}{40} = 8.1 \quad (19)$$

Capacitor value, C_1

$$C_1 = \frac{V_o D}{R f \Delta V_{C1}} = \frac{(18)(0.6)}{(8.1)(1.5)(50000)} = 89 \mu\text{H} \quad (20)$$

TABLE 1. Cuk converter parameter

Simulation	Simulation 1	Simulation 2
Input voltage	18	12
Simulation output voltage	12.01	18
Calculation output voltage	12	18
Frequency	50 kHz	50 kHz
Duty Cycle	0.4	0.6
Ripple %	10%	10%
Inductor 1	649 μ H	432 μ H
Inductor 2	432 μ H	649 μ H
Capacitor 1	6.94 μ F	89 μ F
Capacitor 2	64 μ F	4.29 μ F
Load	3.6 Ω	8.1 Ω

FIGURE 4. Open loop Cuk Converter

Figure 4 shows Cuk converter in MATLAB/SIMULINK. This circuit has 2 inductor, 2 capacitor, 2 switch which are MOSFET, diode and 3 sensor. The sensor that has been used in the circuit are voltage sensor and current sensor to detect the value of currents and voltage at the load for analysis. All the parameter that has been calculated and determined has been inserted in the circuit to do simulation.

Closed Loop Controller Cuk Converter

By definition, power converters are non-linear, with a different structure for each switching cycle. Due to saturating inductance and voltage clamping, they have non-linearity difficulties. The efficiency and stability of DC-DC converters suffer as a result of this non-linearity. The primary goal of the control action is to put the system's steady-state and dynamic behaviour within well-defined bounds of steady-state error, overshoot, and settling time, while also improving response and stability.

The converters switching losses are reduced by having a good dynamic responsive. For the control of DC-DC converters, a variety of linear and non-linear controllers are used. Although linear converters are simple and straightforward to use, they are poor in dealing with system parameter change. In order to overcome these drawbacks, a various type of controller are developed in this study which is PI, OCC and FLC. All the the parameter are same for the three controller to get best analysis on output voltage.

PI controller

FIGURE 5. Cuk converter with PI controller

Figure 5 shows Cuk circuit with PI controller. Output voltage errors enter back to the MOSFET after the voltage has been compensated by the PI block. Two ways to determined value K_p and K_I which are Ziegler Nichols second method and heuristical method. For this circuit heuristical method has been chosen to get the value K_p and K_I because the output voltage using heuristical method has better overshoot in output voltage compare to ziegler nichols second method. Heuristical method is any approach to problem solving or self-discovery that employs a practical method that is not guaranteed to be optimal, perfect, or rational. The most fundamental heuristic is trial and error, by entering value K_p and K_I manually and at the same time output voltage was observed to get the best result. Reference voltage also has been used to subtract the output voltage in the second scope, if the value in the second scope is zero, the error in output voltage has been successfully compensated.

OCC Controller

Figure 6 depicts a one-cycle control technique's basic circuit. The clock signal is generated via a resettable integrator, a comparator, an SR flip-flop, and an oscillator (clock). Let $U(t)$ be the input signal, and $W(t)$ be the output signal. In a single switching cycle of the switch 'SW,' the desired averaged output value is produced. The oscillator determines the switching period T_s (constant) using the clock signal. For a time T_{on} the switch is closed and $W(t)=U(t)$. When T_{off} the switch is opened and $W(t)=0$. Thus the average value of output is same as the average of an input signal over ON period. Figure 6 is the concept of OCC controller and Figure 7 is OCC in MATLAB/SIMULINK.

$$W = \frac{1}{T_s} \int W(t) dt = \frac{1}{T_s} \int_0^{T_{on}} U(t) dt \quad (21)$$

Where \bar{W} = The average value of output $W(t)$ = Instantaneous value of Output signal $U(t)$ = Instantaneous value of Input signal T_s = Switching Period

FIGURE 6. OCC Controller concept

FIGURE 7. Cuk Converter with OCC controller

FLC Controller

Fuzzy logic-based controllers are currently used in practically every industry, from vehicle brake systems to washing machines, freezers, and factory quality control systems. From figure 8 the error and change of error enter the FLC block to compensate the error before entering the MOSFET for complete the cycle.

In this rule base in FLC block, “e” represents error, “de” represents error change and “du”

represents output. The terms Negative Big (NB), Negative Small (NS), Zero Error(ZZ), Positive Small (PS), and Positive Big (PB) are all terms used to describe the rules in FLC blocks. The following is a quick summary of how fuzzy control rules work. When a system's output is lower and farther than the stated reference point, indicating a significant positive error, the controller must immediately increase the output voltage.

Figure 8. FLC controller

Table 2 Base rule in FLC block

Error/ change of error	Negative Big (NB)	Negative Small (NS)	Zero Error(ZZ)	Positive Small (PS)	Positive Big (PB)
Negative Big (NB)	Positive Big (PB)	Positive Big (PB)	Positive Big (PB)	Positive Small (PS)	Positive Small (PS)
Negative Small (NS)	Positive Big (PB)	Positive Small (PS)	Positive Small (PS)	Positive Small (PS)	Zero Error(ZZ)
Zero Error(ZZ)	Positive Small (PS)	Positive Small (PS)	Zero Error(ZZ)	Negative Small (NS)	Negative Small (NS)
Positive Small (PS)	Zero Error(ZZ)	Negative Small (NS)	Negative Small (NS)	Negative Small (NS)	Negative Big (NB)
Positive Big (PB)	Negative Small (NS)	Negative Big (NB)	Negative Big (NB)	Negative Big (NB)	Negative Big (NB)

Dynamic response Cuk converter

Two important factors influencing the dynamic response are the control loop(s) and the dc-dc converter topology. By an optimized design on the control loop compensator the dynamics can be improved. After designing the best circuit , two reference point were choose to make sure high performance cuk converter can operate in two mode which are Buck and Boost. For PI and OCC controller before 0.3 seconds reference voltage were set to 10 V and after 0.3 second the reference were

change to 50 V to make sure the converter can operate in Boost mode. For FLC the reference voltage were set same as PI and OCC but the voltage reference change after 0.03 seconds. All the output voltage were observed and make comparison based on settling time, rise time, ripple percentage and stability.

Parameter closed loop

All the three converter has same parameter as Table 3 for make sure when do comparison, the result observed were analyze fairly. The parameter was choose because the component value are easy to do and realistic for doing hardware.

Table 3 Cuk converter for all controller			
Controller	PI	OCC	FLC
Vin(V)	40	40	40
Vout(V)	10	10	10
L1	0.1mH	0.1mH	0.1mH
L2	0.1mH	0.1mH	0.1mH
C1	1000 μ F	1000 μ F	1000 μ F
C2	1000 μ F	1000 μ F	1000 μ F
F	50 kHz	50 kHz	50 kHz
R	18 Ω	18 Ω	18 Ω

RESULT

Open Loop Cuk Converter

Figure 9 Output voltage for duty cycle 0.4

Figure 10 Output voltage for duty cycle 0.6

When duty cycle 0.4 in Figure 9, output voltage form in simulation is 12 V and this shows this Cuk converter in mode Buck has reducing input voltage from 18 V. For duty cycle 0.6 in Figure 10, output voltage form shows that Cuk converter act as Boost converter that increase the input voltage from 12 V to 18 V. This shows that duty cycle effect the output voltage of Cuk converter.

Closed Loop Cuk Converter with PI,OCC and FLC controller

Figure 11 Output voltage PI controller

Figure 12 Output voltage OCC controller

Figure 13 Output voltage FLC controller

Controller	PI	OCC	FLC
Rise time(ms)	29.461	39.321	0.009
%overshoot voltage	0.275	230	15
Settling time	0.0611s	0.0811s	0.012s
%Ripple	5	3	7
%Steady state error	1	2	5

For output voltage PI controller in Figure 11, PI controller has rise time and settling time second lowest compare to other controllers. Primary advantages for PI controller, it has minimum overshoot voltage and steady state error base on table 4. This shows, If the system doesn't need a fast response but an accuracy needed, so the PI controller is the best controller for the system. Based on simulation, when frequency chosen is less than 50 kHz, settling time will decreases but the ripple percentage on output voltage increases.

Figure 12 shows output voltage simulation on OCC controller that has highest value rise time, settling time and overshoot voltage compare others controller. Advantages for OCC it has less ripple percentage compare others controller. OCC is the most complex controller because it has many components and follows period cycle that has been control by SR flip-flop. Thus, OCC has highest overshoot voltage which is 230%. On top of that, system that suitable for OCC is system that focus on accuracy and ripple percentage. When frequency value less than 50 kHz, steady state error will reduce but after 40 kHz, output voltage become zero.

Based on output voltage in Figure 13, FLC output voltage has lowest rise time and settling time compare to others controller. Unfortunately, FLC has highest steady state error compare others controller. FLC is the simplest controller compare others because it operates base on rule base but unfortunately it has highest steady state error due the system operating on rule base that need expertise to choose the rules. The method for determine the rules are heustirical method which means try and error. FLC is the best controller for the system that require speed but not accuracy.

TABLE 4. Dynamic response for output voltage with controller PI, OCC and FLC

Based on all the simulation, ripple percentage in all controller can be reduced by changing value of inductor, load and frequency on Cuk controller.

Dynamic response for Cuk controller

FIGURE 14. Dynamic response PI controller

FIGURE 14. Dynamic response OCC controller

FIGURE 14. Dynamic response FLC controller

Table 5 Characteristic of output voltage when reference voltage change

Controller	PI	OCC	FLC
Settling time	0.06s	0.04s	0.03s
Rise time	0.056s	0.032s	0.024s
% Ripple	8%	5%	6%
Stability	stable	stable	stable

All the output voltage in Figure 14, Figure 15 and Figure 16 for three controllers are stable because the output voltage follows the reference voltage when the reference voltage change and output voltage stay at the same level as reference voltage. This show the circuit that has been designed can do both mode which is Buck and Boost. This controller also fulfills characteristic to become high performance controller.

From Table 5, FLC has settling time and rise time lowest follows by OCC and PI. For steady state error PI has lowest value and best accuracy to follow reference voltage.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Cuk converter can do both mode which are Buck and Boost. For open loop, duty cycle plays essential role for determine output voltage value. It also can be seen open loop output voltage is not robust and has higher ripple percentage that why a controller needed to solve the problem. In closed loop, the best performance based on speed are FLC because it has lowest rise time and settling time in output voltage. In term of accuracy, PI is the most accurate because it has lowest steady state error in output voltage. OCC controller has lowest ripple percentage but has highest overshoot output voltage.

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